

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Organic and conventional farmers' perceptions of the quality of their soils in Estonia

Organic farming can contribute to improving soil health and soil quality, topics that are the focal concerns in the EU Soil Strategy, as previous land management practices have resulted in soil degradation in the EU. Estonia is one of the countries in which the share of land under organic farming has increased rapidly over the last ten years, reaching 23% by 2021 already. However, the topic of how the selection of organic or conventional farming is related to the farmers' understanding of their soils and crop selection has not received much attention.

To analyze what the relationship is between crop production and farmers' opinions on their soil quality in two agricultural systems, we examined the data collected with a questionnaire survey from 276 farms in Estonia in the project SoildiverAgro. Around one-third of responses were collected from the organic

farmers. The survey results indicated that 42% of conventional and 27% of organic farmers in the study assessed their soil quality as good or very good. The most common answer given by farmers was that their soil quality is fair (49% of conventional farmers and 60% of organic farmers). The regression results showed a correlation between the type of crop and the soil quality scores. The farmers who grew wheat gave their soil quality lower scores, whereas rapeseed farming increased scores for soil quality for both organic and conventional agricultural systems, demonstrating the farmers' perceptions on the quality of their soil affects their choice of crops. The analysis did not find a significant relationship between the scores on the soil quality and whether or not the Estonian farmers in their study had converted part of their land to grassland.

1. Organic cereal field after harvest; SoildiverAgro CS12 in Estonia, Nemoral region. Photo: Shanskiy, M.

KEYWORDS

Soil management, farm survey, organic farming

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